

Analysis of factors influencing farmers' insecticide sprays

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Farmers' overestimation of yield loss due to pests and their perceptions that insecticides are remedies probably account for much of the unnecessary insecticide use in rice. Understanding some of the factors that influence farmers' decisions to spray may improve the development of management strategies.

We analyzed insecticide spray patterns of 285 rice farmers in San Jose, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in relation to their knowledge of natural enemies, perceptions of yield losses due to pest damage, attitudes toward insecticide use, and whether they have undergone training. Farmers were grouped into those who spray early, spray frequently, and those who do neither. Those who applied insecticides within the first 40 d after crop establishment were classified as early sprayers and the rest as nonearly sprayers. Likewise, farmers who applied insecticides more than four times in one cropping season were classified as frequent sprayers and those who sprayed four times or less as nonfrequent sprayers.

Knowledge of beneficial insects was assessed based on farmers' awareness of natural enemies and their roles, and farmers' perceived effects of insecticides on them. Pest management training was evaluated based on attendance and topics of trainings attended. Attitudes toward insecticide use were grouped into "in favor" and "not in favor" based on their responses to statements on insecticide perceptions. Farmers who perceived that insecticides must be applied to the rice crop, increase rice yields, do not cause pest resurgence, and are effective in controlling pests were classified as in favor.

Knowledge, perception, attitude, and training variables were tested independently for associations with early and frequent spraying variables using the chi-square test.

Associations of knowledge with early and frequent spraying and of training with early and frequent spraying were not

Table 1. Associations between spraying behavior and knowledge of natural enemies and perceptions/attitudes toward insecticide use of farmers in San Jose, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1994.

Association	n	df	χ^2	P
<i>Early spraying with</i>				
knowledge of natural enemies	1	285	2.37	0.12
pest management training	1	285	3.01	0.08
perception of yield loss	1	285	0.15	0.70
attitude toward pesticide use	1	285	26.22	<.01
<i>Frequent spraying with</i>				
knowledge of natural enemies	1	285	0.08	0.78
pest management training	1	285	0.31	0.58
perception of yield loss	1	285	4.04	0.04
attitude toward pesticide use	1	285	16.36	<.01

Table 2. Probabilities of farmers' sprayresponses as affected by yield loss perception and attitude toward insecticide use. San Jose, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1994.

Spray frequently	Yield loss due to leaf damage	Response ^a frequency	Probability
No	No	111	0.42
No	Yes	57	0.21
Yes	No	77	0.29
Yes	Yes	22	0.08
Spray early	Favor insecticides	Response frequency	Probability
No	No	18	0.06
No	Yes	3	0.01
Yes	No	48	0.17
Yes	Yes	216	0.76
Spray frequently	Favor insecticides	Response frequency	Probability
No	No	56	0.20
No	Yes	122	0.43
Yes	No	10	0.04
Yes	Yes	97	0.34

^aFarmers with no response were excluded from the analysis.

significant (Table 1). This implies that pest management training and knowledge of beneficial insects did not influence farmers' spray patterns. However, association tests between knowledge and attitude variables revealed a tendency for farmers without knowledge of natural enemies to favor the use of insecticides ($c^2 = 4.03$, $P = 0.5$). This implies that although lack of knowledge of natural enemies does not seem to influence unnecessary spraying, it may still have an indirect effect because farmers who favor insecticide use tend to be the ones who lack this knowledge.

Attitudes favoring insecticide use were highly associated with early and frequent spraying. The probabilities that farmers who favored insecticide use would spray early and frequently were

0.76 and 0.34, respectively (Table 2). The perception that yield loss is caused by leaf damage is likewise associated with frequent spraying. Farmers who did not think yield loss was due to leaf damage tended not to spray frequently ($P = 0.42$).

Our analyses showed that attitudes favoring insecticide use seem to be more important than lack of knowledge and training in influencing farmers to spray early as well as frequently. To improve current farmer practices and to reduce pesticide misuse, strategies need to emphasize changing farmers' attitudes that favor insecticide use. These might include changing farmers' perceptions that insecticides are necessary inputs, increase yields, do not harm rice, and are effective in controlling pests. ■